

Quinazolines: Part VII*. Synthesis of Some Pyrrolo [1,2-a]quinazoline-5 (4H)-thiones

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Pyrrolo[1,2-a]quinazoline-5(4H)-thiones have been synthesised by the cyclisation of reaction intermediates of 2-bromomethyl-3-phenylquinazoline-4(3H)-thione with active methylené compounds.

We have recently reported¹ the synthesis of some pyrrolo[1,2-a]quinazoline-5-(4H)-ones. Because of our interest in the bridge-head nitrogen heterocycles incorporating a 4-quinazolone ring we extended this reaction to quinazoline-4-thione system which is the subject matter of this communication.

2-Bromomethyl-3-phenylquinazoline-4(3H)-thione (II), the starting material, was prepared by the fusion of 2-methyl-3-phenylquinazoline-4(3H)-one (I) with phosphorous pentasulphide and subsequent treatment with N-bromosuccinimide.

II : R = Br

III : R = H

IV : R = CH $\begin{cases} \text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5 \\ \text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5 \end{cases}$

V : R = CH $\begin{cases} \text{COCH}_3 \\ \text{COCH}_3 \end{cases}$

VI : R = CH $\begin{cases} \text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5 \\ \text{COCH}_3 \end{cases}$

* Part VI. S. K. P. Sinha and B. D. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 743.

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Treatment of the starting material II with sodio derivatives of diethylmalonate, acetyl acetone and ethyl acetoacetate gave respectively 2-(2',2'-diethoxycarbonyl ethyl)-3-phenylquinazoline-4(3H)-thione (IV), 2-(2',2'-diacetyl ethyl)-3-phenylquinazoline-4(3H)-thione (V) and 2-(2'-acetyl-2'-ethoxycarbonyl ethyl)-3-phenylquinazoline-4(3H)-thione (VI). These intermediates on treatment with polyphosphoric acid afforded the corresponding pyrroloquinazoline thiones, *viz.*, 2-carbethoxy-4-phenyl-5(4H)-thionopyrrolo[1,2-a]quinazoline-1(2H)-one (VII), 2-acetyl-1-methyl-4-phenylpyrrolo[1,2-a]quinazoline-5(4H)-thione (VIII) and 2-carbethoxy-1-methyl-4-phenylpyrrolo[1,2-a]quinazoline-5(4H)-thione (IX)]. Thus the reaction

VII

VIII : R = COCH₃; R₁ = CH₃IX : R = COOC₂H₅; R₁ = CH₃

appears to proceed through the mechanism already postulated earlier in the case of oxo-analogues¹.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the m.p.s were determined in open capillaries in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. P.P.A. used was of laboratory reagent grade. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60°–80°.

2-Methyl-3-phenylquinazoline-4(3H)-thione (III): Equimolar mixture of I and P₂S₅ was melted in a conical flask fitted with Liebig's condenser at 155°–160°, the temperature was maintained for a further period of ½ hr. and then cooled. Before solidification, the melt was extracted with benzene, excess of the solvent distilled off and the residual solution on cooling deposited yellow crystalline solid. It was collected and crystallised from benzene to give III as shining yellow needles (2 g.; 79%), m.p. 186°–187° (lit.² m.p. 186°).

2-Bromomethyl-3-phenylquinazoline-4(3H)-thione (II): To a solution of III (2.52 g.; 0.01 mole) in CHCl₃ (10 ml) was added freshly prepared NBS (1.78g; 0.01 mole) followed by benzoyl peroxide (0.02 g.) when exothermic reaction started. It was shaken well and after 15 min. the solid began to separate. The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for a further period of 0.5 hr., filtered and washed. The residual solid on two crystallisations from acetic acid gave II as pink white needles (2.1 g.; 65%), m.p. 300° (decomp.). ν_{max} (KBr), 695, 760, 1370, 1725, 2500–2600 cm⁻¹ λ_{max} (EtOH) 232 nm (Found : C, 54.3; H, 3.2; N, 8.3; Br, 24.20. C₁₅H₁₁N₂BrS requires C, 54.4; H, 3.3; N, 8.4; Br, 24.1%).

2-(2',2'-Diethoxycarbonyl ethyl)-3-phenylquinazoline-4(3H)-thione (IV): Na (0.25 g.) in dry MeOH (20 ml.) was treated with freshly distilled diethyl malonate (1.6 ml.; 0.011 mole) and to resulting stirred solution of which II (3.31 g.; 0.01 mole) in dry MeOH (30 ml.) was

added dropwise. After the addition was over, the reaction mixture was stirred for one more hour and kept overnight. It was then diluted with water and cooled when yellow solid separated out. This was collected, washed and crystallised twice from isopropanol to afford IV as yellow shining needles (2.8 g.; 70%), m.p. 170°–171°, ν_{max} (KBr) 1255, 1300, 1363, 1400, 1470, 1602, 1700 cm^{-1} λ_{max} (EtOH) 221, 360 nm (ϵ_{max} 60670, 21440). Found : C, 64.3; H, 5.5; N, 6.7. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires C, 64.4; H, 5.4; N, 6.8%.

2-(2',2'-Diacetylethyl)-3-phenylquinazoline-4(3H)-thione (V) : To a stirred solution of Na (0.50 g.) in dry MeOH (40 ml) acetyl acetone (2 ml.; 2 g.; 0.02 mole) and methanolic solution (40 ml.) of II (6.64 g.; 0.02 mole) were successively added dropwise and the stirring continued for one more hour. Next day when worked up as in the previous case yellow solid was obtained. It was crystallised from isopropanol to give V as yellow prismatic needles (3.0 g.; 85%), m.p. 181°–182°. ν_{max} (KBr) 1250, 1305, 1360, 1465, 1605 cm^{-1} λ_{max} (EtOH) 221, 360 nm (ϵ_{max} 49220, 20930). (Found : C, 68.5; H, 5.2; N, 7.8. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 68.6; H, 5.1; N, 8.0%).

2-(2'-Acetyl-2'-ethoxycarbonylethyl)-3-phenylquinazoline-4(3H)-thione (VI) : II (3.31 g.; 0.01 mole) in dry MeOH (30 ml.) was added dropwise with stirring to a mixture of Na (0.25 g.) in MeOH (20 ml.) treated with freshly distilled acetoacetic ester (1.3 ml; 0.01 mole) and the stirring continued for a further period of 1 hr. The reaction mixture was kept overnight, diluted with water, cooled and extracted with ether (15 ml. \times 3). The ether layer was dried (Na_2SO_4), distilled and the residual solid on crystallisation from MeOH yielded VI as yellow needles, (3.1 g.; 80%), m.p. 163°–164° ν_{max} (KBr) 1330, 1385, 1690, 1705 cm^{-1} λ_{max} (EtOH) 227, 265 nm (ϵ_{max} 53920, 22540). (Found : C, 66.2; H, 5.1; N, 7.3. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$ requires C, 66.3; H, 5.3; N, 7.4%).

2-Carbethoxy-4-phenyl-5(4H)-thionopyrrolo[1,2-a]quinazoline-1(2H)-one (VII) : A mixture of IV (2 g.) and PPA (10 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 125°–130° for 0.5 hr, the solution diluted with water, cooled and the yellow solid that separated out was filtered, washed successively with water, dilute NaOH and crystallised from MeOH twice to give VII as rectangular plates, (1 g.; 56%), m.p. 186°–187°. ν_{max} (KBr) 1250, 1290, 1363, 1475, 1600 cm^{-1} λ_{max} (MeOH) 225 nm (ϵ_{max} , 30440). (Found : C, 65.8; H, 4.2; N, 7.6. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$ requires C, 65.9; H, 4.4; N, 7.7%).

2-Acetyl-1-methyl-4-phenylpyrrolo [1,2-a]quinazoline-5(4H)-thione (VIII) : V (2 g.) was thoroughly mixed with PPA (10 g.) and heated in an oil bath at 130°–135° for 1 hr. It was diluted with water, cooled, the solid that separated was filtered, washed repeatedly with water and crystallised twice from MeOH— C_6H_6 to furnish VIII as yellow shining needles (1.4 g.; 75%), m.p. 187°–188° ν_{max} (KBr) 1245, 1325, 1363, 1400, 1460, 1600, 1690 cm^{-1} λ_{max} (MeOH) 233 nm (ϵ_{max} , 25460). (Found : C, 72.4; H, 4.7; N, 8.3. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{OS}$ requires C, 72.3; H, 4.8; N, 8.4%).

It formed a 2 : 4 DNP derivative which on crystallisation from MeOH gave pink needles, m.p. 234°–235.°

2-Carbethoxy-1-methyl-4-phenylpyrrolo[1,2-a]quinazoline-5(4H)-thione (IX) : A thorough mixture of VI (1 g.) in PPA (10 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 130°–140° for 1 hr. The orange coloured reaction mixture when diluted with water and cooled, separated as a pale

yellow solid. It was filtered, washed with water several times and crystallised from MeOH to give IX as shining pale yellow rhombic plates (0.7 g; 77%), m.p. 184°–185°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1245, 1300, 1363, 1460, 1600, 1675 cm^{-1} λ_{max} (EtOH) 222 nm (ϵ_{max} , 44670). (Found: C, 69.5; H, 5.0; N, 7.6. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 69.6; H, 4.9; N, 7.7%).

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